

Power converter parameter prediction based on Extended Kalman Filter

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In space power systems, high levels of reliability are required to not jeopardize the objective of the mission. With the purpose of increasing their lifetimes, a non-invasive health monitoring method is presented that estimates the parasitic resistance of the converters that conform the power subsystem. This parasitic resistance increases when the system degrades. This method is based on the use of an extended Kalman filter. By taking measurements already required either by the control stage or for telemetry purposes, it is demonstrated that it is possible to detect an increase in parasitic resistance in the converter. The implementation of this method has been validated both through simulation and experimentally.

1 Introduction

The Electrical Power Subsystem (EPS) in a satellite follows the diagram of Figure 1. It consists mainly of the Solar Array Regulator (SAR), which extracts energy from the solar array, the Battery Charge Regulator (BCR) Battery Discharge Regulator (BDR), that inject energy to and from the battery, respectively [1]. Via the power bus, these blocks supply power to the rest of the subsystems and the payload.

These blocks are based on DC/DC converters, that have different power and voltage specifications. By means of utilizing switching elements, typically MOSFETs, they provide a stable voltage and current output from a wide range of input voltages and currents [2]. The losses in these power converter can be classified into conduction losses and switching losses [3]. A key source of conduction losses is the conduction resistance R_{on} that appears when the switching elements are conducting. This parameter is also useful for detecting converter degradation [4], as the switching devices are one of the most likely to fail [5]. Prior to failure, the switching element experiments an increase in its R_{on} resistance [6]. The limit before total failure is generally considered a 12% increase rela-

Figure 1: Power subsystem block diagram.

tive to the nominal value [7]. Adding additional circuits to measure R_{on} is undesirable, as it introduces more elements that could fail, in addition to increasing the number of components and their associated costs. Therefore, indirect methods that can estimate the value of R_{on} from signals normally used by the control stage of the converter are preferred[8]. The Kalman filter and its variations for non-linear environments, such as the extended Kalman filter (EKF)[9], are techniques that estimate the state of a dynamic system from noisy measurements [10]. The procedure consists, first, of a prediction step where the next sample is estimated, and then a correction step based on the sample measurement. Its areas of application are varied [11][12]. Within power electronics, its use has been more restricted to motor control [13] or to determine the battery charge state [14]. They have also been used as estimators when the use of sensors is difficult[15]. Applications focused on parameter estimation in converters have been proposed in several studies [16][17]. R_{on} based estimations are explained in [18], but using the averaged model and in open loop control. [8] provides a review of several state of the art techniques, but they either require actual measurement of the R_{on} or the point of operation of the converter is modified. The method proposed in this paper allows to predict the R_{on} value during regular operation, without the need of required circuitry.

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Also, in comparison with other data-centered methods, training is not needed. The case study of this work is modular satellite power systems [19], where several parallel converters regulate the bus voltage. In this way, a forecasting method is implemented to predict when one of the modules has degraded more than expected, the load demand provided by this module can be reduced and compensated with the other modules. This method is based on the prediction of the resistance value R_{on} of the switching elements, allowing less power to be drawn from the module, and extending its lifespan. Although it is a very specific application, a general methodology is proposed and the proposed estimation system could be adapted to almost any controlled DC/DC converter. This methodology to estimate the health status of the converter would be of help in the Fault Detection, Isolation and Recovery (FDIR) approach. This article is organized into the following sections. Section 2 discusses the operation of the utilized DC-DC converter, in this case a step up boost converter. Section 3 focuses on the application of the extended Kalman filter application to predict the R_{on} value. Section 4 contains the experimental results obtained. After that, Section 5 provides the a discussion of the findings of this paper. Finally, Section 6 includes the main conclusions of this work.

2 Boost converter

The converter analyzed in this case is the step up boost converter, following the schematics of Figure 2. This converter increases its output voltage with respect to its input by a factor

$$V_o = V_{in} \cdot \frac{1}{1-d} \tag{1}$$

where d is the time that switching MOSFET M_1 is turned on with respect to the switching period T_s , defined as duty cycle [2]. During $d \cdot T_s$, the inductor current I_L increases, and during $(1-d) \cdot T_s$ this current decreases, as Figure 3 shows. The case study is parallel modular converters connected to provide the same output voltage, so one module can compensate for another in case the latter is damaged. Hence, for this study it is considered that the output voltage V_o is a constant voltage source. This set of converters is controlled by taking a sample of the current that goes through the inductor I_L and makes it equal to a reference value I_{ref} . The value of the conduction resistances of the switching elements R_{on} , as well as the rest of the parasitic elements of the circuit, are contained in the resistance r_l . This parasitic resistance is the parameter that is estimated and can be used as a basis to detect changes in the overall R_{on} . In addition,

Figure 2: Boost converter circuit

Figure 3: Inductor current sampling instants.

a second current value through the inductor called I_{rip} is sampled, taken during the same period T_s , as shown in Figure 3. This is utilized to detect changes in the ripple of the current circulating through the inductor that may indicate changes in r_l . The difference between the two current samples I_{ref} and I_{rip} results in the observable state Δi , used by the EKF to obtain a second non-observable state that contains the prediction of r_l .

The converter has two switching states, following the switching sequence of M_1 (Figure 4). During dT_s switch M_1 is closed. It opens at dT_s , and stays opened during $(1-d)T_s$ M_1 . Then, the system can be described as

$$\Delta \dot{i} = \begin{cases} \frac{V_{in}}{L} - \frac{r_l}{L} \cdot \Delta i - \frac{r_l}{L} \cdot I_{ref} & \text{if } 0 < t < d \cdot T_s \\ \frac{V_{in}}{L} - \frac{V_o}{L} - \frac{r_l}{L} \cdot \Delta i - \frac{r_l}{L} \cdot I_{ref} & \text{if } d \cdot T_s < t < T_s \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Figure 4: Boost converter operation during dT_s (top) and during $(1-d)T_s$ (bottom).

where the states are $\begin{bmatrix} \Delta i \\ r_l \end{bmatrix}$ and the control input is $\begin{bmatrix} V_{in} \\ V_o \\ I_{ref} \end{bmatrix}$. This description is used to determine the state function that is subsequently used in the EKF to predict the states.

2.1 State propagation

As it was mentioned earlier, the system consists of two states. One observable, Δi , which contains the difference between the current value used for the control reference I_{ref} and a second sample I_{rip} . The other state, an unobservable one, belongs to the parasitic resistance r_l . This is what is called an augmented state. This augmented state has no dynamics, so $\dot{r}_l = 0$.

To know how a state evolves in the next switching period, it is necessary to propagate it during a clock cycle T_s , where

$$\Delta i(T_s) = e^{-\frac{r_l}{L} T_s} \cdot \Delta i(0) + \int_0^{T_s} e^{-\frac{r_l}{L} (T_s - \tau)} \cdot B(\tau) \cdot \begin{bmatrix} V_{in} \\ V_{out} \\ I_{ref} \end{bmatrix} d\tau \quad (3)$$

that results in the state transition $F(X[n], U[n])$ as a function of the input $U[n]$ and the state variables $X[n]$.

3 EKF implementation

3.1 Development of the EKF

In this way, the EKF can be derived, following the process shown in Figure 5. The states are $\Delta i[n]$ and $r_l[n]$. The input variables are the input voltage $V_{in}[n]$, output voltage $V_{out}[n]$ and the reference current $I_{ref}[n]$.

With this, the state function $F(X[n], U[n]) = X[n+1]$ can be derived. The measurement matrix $H(X[n])$ represents the states as seen by the sensors. As the system is non-linear, the EKF linearizes the state transition function with respect to the previous state, which

implies that it is necessary to calculate the Jacobian matrix of both the process and the measurement $J_F[n]$ and $J_H[n]$. They are used to predict the state covariance.

The covariance matrices of the process error Q and the measurement R model the noise of the entire system. These values are usually determined empirically[20]. This matrix allows to know how much confidence there is in the predicted values and models the uncertainty introduced by the system.

The covariance matrix P indicates the confidence that is had in the EKF state estimates. This matrix is updated in each iteration in the prediction stage, incorporating the process error (matrix Q). In the correction stage, P is further adjusted by adding information from the measurements through the Kalman gain.

In this way, the iterative process of the EKF can be initiated, going through the stages of: initialization, prediction, and correction of values.

- *Initialization:* The EKF receives an initial estimation of the states X_0 and the covariance matrix P_0 indicating the uncertainty in that estimation.
- *Prediction:* the EKF makes predictions of the states $\Delta i^f[n]$ and $r_l^f[n]$ and of the covariance matrix $P^f[n]$, from the matrix of the corrected previous states. The prediction of the covariance matrix is made from the Jacobian of $J_F[n]$
- *Correction:* the Kalman gain $K[n]$ is calculated to adjust the predicted values with the measured ones.

4 Experimental results

In this section, the experimentally obtained results are collected. Validation has been performed with a boost converter on which the values of input and output voltages, duty cycles, and currents through the inductor are captured. Additionally, this converter includes extra circuitry to measure the voltages and currents

Figure 5: Kalman filter algorithm block diagram.

Figure 6: Experimental setup.

of the switching MOSFET and thus the R_{on} for comparison with the estimated values. The acquisition of all these data is conducted using a Texas Instruments TMS320F28379, which also handles the converter control, forcing a constant value of average inductor current of 2.5 A.

These data, along with the voltage and current of the switching MOSFET, are sent to an external device containing the MATLAB Simulink model of the EKF. The block diagram of the experimental implementation is shown in Figure 6. The selected MOSFET is the SPP20N60S5, with an R_{on} of 0.19 m Ω . A switching frequency of 10 kHz has been chosen to avoid data transmission losses to the MATLAB equipment.

Figure 7 shows the data used as input for the EKF. It includes a fixed output voltage V_{out} of 30 V, an input voltage V_{in} ranging from 15-17 V, the current samples I_{ref} and I_{rip} , with I_{ref} being the reference current for control, and duty cycle d . With these data, the prediction is made. Figure 8 shows the estimated difference

Figure 7: Input to the EKF.

Figure 8: Output of the EKF.

between the two current samples through the inductor $\Delta i_{(est)}$ versus the real value Δi , and the augmented state $r_{l(est)}$ corresponding to the estimated parasitic resistance of the system, versus the real R_{on} . In this case, from 35 s onwards, the R_{on} is increased artificially. This is observed in the estimation given by the EKF, which predicts an increase in the parasitic resistance $r_{l(est)}$ detecting this sudden change. This increase is 10%, implying an aged MOSFET at the limit of failure.

5 Discussion

With this method, detecting changes in internal converter parameters without the need of invasive direct measurements has been validated. This method proves useful in critical environments such as space[6], where modern trends bet on the use of modular topologies that allow more flexibility in power demands [19]. It also raises new knowledge into the equation to use the Extended Kalman Filter as an estimation method in closed loop converters, as opposed to [18]. Additionally, the use of EKF has an advantage over other data-based methods shown in [8], which is that in this case computation-intensive resources spent in training are not required. Although the EKF estimates the total parasitic resistance of the converter, this research study focused on estimation changes that are in line with R_{on} changes. Future works are encouraged to expand this method by optimizing failure detection, excluding other undesirable effects such as temperature.

6 Conclusions

In this work, a method for predicting an increase in the R_{on} of the switching MOSFETs present in power converters is presented with the aim of extending their remaining useful lifetime. This method is based

on the use of an extended Kalman filter as a predictor. From simple measurements at system level it is possible to predict when one of the elements has been degraded. The validation of this method has been carried out experimentally using a boost converter and the EKF calculation has been performed through the MATLAB tool that processes the data collected in an external device. The results allow determining an increase in the system's parasitic resistance which would be sufficient to determine that the MOSFET has undergone premature aging.

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References

- O'Sullivan, D. Space Power Electronics, Design Drivers (1). *EPE Journal* **3**, 85–92. ISSN: 0939-8368, 2376-9319 (Jan. 1993).
- Erickson, R. W. & Maksimović, D. *Fundamentals of Power Electronics* ISBN: 978-3-030-43879-1 978-3-030-43881-4 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020).
- Ivanovic, Z., Blanusa, B. & Knezic, M. *Power Loss Model for Efficiency Improvement of Boost Converter* in 2011 XXIII International Symposium on Information, Communication and Automation Technologies 2011 XXIII International Symposium on Information, Communication and Automation Technologies (Oct. 2011), 1–6.
- Wang, H. & Blaabjerg, F. Power Electronics Reliability: State of the Art and Outlook. *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics* **9**, 6476–6493. ISSN: 2168-6785. <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9253639> (2024) (Dec. 2021).
- Ferreira Costa, L. & Liserre, M. Failure Analysis of the Dc-Dc Converter: A Comprehensive Survey of Faults and Solutions for Improving Reliability. *IEEE Power Electronics Magazine* **5**, 42–51. ISSN: 2329-9207, 2329-9215 (Dec. 2018).
- Celaya, J. R., Saxena, A., Saha, S., Vashchenko, V. & Goebel, K. *Prognostics of Power MOSFET* in 2011 IEEE 23rd International Symposium on Power Semiconductor Devices and ICs ICPSD (IEEE, San Diego, CA, USA, May 2011), 160–163. ISBN: 978-1-4244-8425-6.
- Dusmez, S., Bhardwaj, M., Sun, L. & Akin, B. In Situ Condition Monitoring of High-Voltage Discrete Power MOSFET in Boost Converter Through Software Frequency Response Analysis. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* **63**, 7693–7702. ISSN: 0278-0046, 1557-9948 (Dec. 2016).
- Kathribail, P. S. & Vijayakumar, T. Comprehensive Study of MOSFET Degradation in Power Converters and Prognostic Failure Detection Using Physical Model. *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series B* **104**, 305–317. ISSN: 2250-2114 (Feb. 1, 2023).
- Simon, D. Kalman Filtering with State Constraints: A Survey of Linear and Nonlinear Algorithms. *IET Control Theory & Applications* **4**, 1303–1318. ISSN: 1751-8644, 1751-8652 (Aug. 1, 2010).
- Senne, K. Stochastic Processes and Filtering Theory. *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* **17**, 752–753. ISSN: 1558-2523 (Oct. 1972).
- Chen, B., Zhang, W.-A. & Yu, L. Distributed Finite-Horizon Fusion Kalman Filtering for Bandwidth and Energy Constrained Wireless Sensor Networks. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing* **62**, 797–812 (2014).
- Lipka, M., Sippel, E. & Vossiek, M. An Extended Kalman Filter for Direct, Real-Time, Phase-Based High Precision Indoor Localization. *IEEE Access* **7**, 25288–25297. ISSN: 2169-3536 (2019).
- Zerdali, E. & Barut, M. The Comparisons of Optimized Extended Kalman Filters for Speed-Sensorless Control of Induction Motors. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* **64**, 4340–4351. ISSN: 0278-0046, 1557-9948 (June 2017).
- Mastali, M. *et al.* Battery State of the Charge Estimation Using Kalman Filtering. *Journal of Power Sources* **239**, 294–307. ISSN: 03787753 (Oct. 2013).
- Haadi, K., Rajaei, A., Shahparasti, M. & Rahideh, A. Sensorless Voltage Observer for a Current-Fed High Step-Up DC-DC Converter Using Extended Kalman Filter. *Electronics* **9**, 2066. ISSN: 2079-9292 (Dec. 4, 2020).
- Missailidis, P., Armstrong, M., Gadoue, S. & Ahmeid, M. *Parameter Estimation of a DC-DC Converter Using a Kalman Filter Approach* in 7th IET International Conference on Power Electronics, Machines and Drives (PEMD 2014) 7th IET International Conference on Power Electronics, Machines and Drives (PEMD 2014) (Institution of Engineering and Technology, Manchester, UK, 2014), 0339–0339. ISBN: 978-1-84919-815-8.
- Beccuti, A. G., Mariethoz, S., Cliquennois, S., Wang, S. & Morari, M. Explicit Model Predictive Control of DC–DC Switched-Mode Power Supplies With Extended Kalman Filtering. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics* **56**, 1864–1874 (2009).
- Alyakhni, A., Al-Mohamad, A. & Hoblos, G. *Joint Estimation of MOSFET Degradation in a DC-DC Converter Using Extended Kalman Filter* in 2019 4th Conference on Control and Fault Tolerant Systems (SysTol) 2019 4th Conference on Control and Fault Tolerant Systems (SysTol) (IEEE, Casablanca, Morocco, Sept. 2019), 319–324. ISBN: 978-1-72810-380-8.
- Zumel, P. *et al.* Digital Control for a Modular System of DC/DC Converters for Primary Distribution System in 2023 13th European Space Power Conference (ESPC) 2023 13th European Space Power Conference (ESPC) (IEEE, Elche, Spain, Oct. 2, 2023), 1–6. ISBN: 9798350328998.
- Schneider, R. & Georgakis, C. How To NOT Make the Extended Kalman Filter Fail. *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research* **52**, 3354–3362. ISSN: 0888-5885, 1520-5045 (Mar. 6, 2013).